

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF 2G AND 5G TECHNOLOGY IN THE FRAMEWORK OF EMERGENCY SITUATIONS

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Abstract

Purpose – The paper aims to compare the radio 5G technologies coverage instead of actual 2G by using MATLAB simulations facilities, with focus on the equipment and coverage area in emergency situations, by comparing performances in ideal conditions and promote the characteristics of the new technology, considering the real case data from the plane crash in Transylvania Apuseni Mountains.

Methodology/approach – The analysis is based on the two different scenarios: 2G and 5G transmitter antennas, using MATLAB software and a free-space ideal propagation model for the coverage areas evaluation.

Findings – The simulations resulted displayed that coverage area with 2G antennas is higher (10,000 meters) compared to the 5G antennas (5,000 meters). Nevertheless, 5G antennas delivered a higher data transfer and a much lower latency, which made them prone for using fast data transmission and the possibility of artificial intelligence embedment.

Research limitations/implications – The case study analysis is based on a simplified MATLAB propagation model. Future work should incorporate more real geospatial data to validate the findings revealed by this initial study.

Practical implications – The findings suggest that implementing a 2G-5G technology hybrid system in mountain regions leverages 2G's broad coverage and 5G's high-speed data transmission. This integration involves placing 2G base stations in valleys, and 5G stations on peaks for optimal coverage.

Originality/value – This study uniquely combines the context of a real-world emergency scenario with a theoretical comparative analysis of 2G and 5G technologies using MATLAB simulations.

Key words: 2G, 5G, emergency.

Introduction

In the last 2 decades the wireless industry has seen an incredible development. More precise, "10,672 articles that mention "5G" in the title, abstract or keywords. These records were authored by 23,695 individuals (estimated) from 108 countries between 2005 and 2020. Items were published in 697 journals (unique ISSNs) and contain 372,623 references to other documents." (Mendonça et al., 2022) Advances in mobile communication technologies from 2G to 5G have significantly enhanced data transmission speeds and reduced latency. "The First generation has fulfilled the basic mobile voice, while the Second generation has dealt with

capacity and coverage. The third generation focused for higher data rate, multimedia support and spread spectrum followed by Fourth generation providing access to wide range of telecommunication services including advanced mobile services, along with a support for low to high mobility application." (Garg, 2014. 186). Now this is very important in emergency situations, such as the plane crash in the Apuseni Mountains that happened on January 20th, 2014. The reliability of these technologies are put to the test, this study delves into a comparative analysis of 2G and 5G antennas using MATLAB simulations, aiming to illustrate their performance and effectiveness in emergency scenarios. "MATLAB is one of the most widely used simulation platforms for academia and research. It contains a powerful 5G toolbox for performing both link-level and system-level simulations." (Xue et al., 2022)

Figure 1. 2G - 5G Hybrid Network

Context of the Apuseni Mountains Plane Crash

On January 20, 2014, at 4:16 p.m., it was announced that an air accident had occurred, announced by one of the passengers at no. 112. The plane accident occurred at an altitude of 1400 m, on the border between Alba and Cluj counties, in conditions of lack of visibility due to fog, but also due to other causes that could not be attributed to the aircraft commander or any other crew member. The aircraft involved in the event belonged to the Civil Aviation Higher School and took off at 13:35 from the "Aurel Vlaicu" International Airport in Bucharest with the destination Oradea International Airport, where it should have landed at 16:35. On board the YR-BNP aircraft, there were 5 people and the pilot, who were traveling from Bucharest to Oradea in order to perform some medical procedures (CIAS. 2014)

Figure 2. YR-BNP plane

The incident highlighted the limitations of the existing emergency communication infrastructure. The area was covered by four 2G antennas but pinpointing the crash site proved challenging due to outdated technologies and inaccurate location data.

Methodology

In order to simulate the coverage area for 2G and 5G antennas, this paper used the MATLAB software to set up the radio transmitters. In the software was created a free-space propagation model, more of a theoretical simulation. The reason for using this methodology was to illustrate the need of new technology implementation in the key domain, especially in emergency response. Panagiotis Gkonis, Panagiotis Trakadas and Dimitra Kaklamani (2020) discussed the importance of accurate channel modeling for MIMO wireless orientations in 5G networks, emphasizing the use of both stochastic and deterministic models. These models are vital for simulating dynamic network configurations, and addressing the complex propagation environments of 5G, thereby supporting diverse applications and improving overall network performance. The following simulations should be a replica of the 2014 incident

Figure 3. 2G Antenna Radio Coverage

2G Simulation Results

- **Frequency:** 900 MHz
- **Reliable Coverage Range:** Up to 2000 meters with strong signal strengths (-80 dBm).
- **Maximum Coverage Range:** Up to 10000 meters with weaker signal strengths (-100 dBm).
- **Advantages:** 2G's lower frequency allows for broader coverage, making it suitable for remote and rugged terrains like mountains.

Figure 4. 5G Antenna Radio Coverage

5G Simulation Results

- **Frequency:** 3.5 GHz
- **Reliable Coverage Range:** Up to 1000 meters with strong signal strengths (-80 dBm).
- **Maximum Coverage Range:** Up to 5000 meters with weaker signal strengths (-100 dBm).
- **Advantages:** 5G's higher frequency provides higher data rates and lower latency, ideal for rapid data transmission and real-time communication.

The results from the above simulations suggest that 2G technology should be used for ensuring wide-area coverage in mountainous regions, maintaining communication in remote areas. On the other hand, given that 5G technology is limited by its range, it should be used in areas where high-speed data transmission is absolutely necessary.

Hybridisation

In valleys and remote areas, 2G base stations provide broad coverage, maintaining connectivity even in challenging conditions. On peaks, 5G stations offer rapid data transmission and low latency, facilitating real-time information sharing and advanced applications like AI. This dual-layer network enhances emergency response effectiveness, ensuring that rescuers have the communication tools they need when every second counts. In this regard, this paper provided a theoretical space-free MATLAB simulation of a 2G – 5G hybridization.

Figure 5. 2G - 5G Hybridisation

After running the simulation, a Coverage Analysis was used - a MATLAB function that can programmatically check if coverage areas intersect or are within a specific distance from each other; featuring the following fig., the result was positive.

```
Command Window
>> Verification
2G site Mătișești and 5G site Vârful Bihor are within coverage range (Distance: 14225.15 meters).
fx >> |
```

Figure 6. Checking if the network mesh has connection

Conclusion

This study provided a comparative analysis of 2G and 5G technologies using MATLAB simulations to evaluate their performance and coverage in emergency situations. The findings demonstrate the critical advantages of each technology: 2G offers extensive coverage, making it suitable for ensuring communication in remote and rugged terrains, while 5G provides higher data rates and lower latency, ideal for rapid data transmission and real-time applications. The concept of 2G - 5G hybridization leverages these strengths, suggesting that a dual-layer network can optimize emergency response systems. By placing 2G base stations in valleys and 5G stations on peaks, this hybrid approach ensures broad, reliable coverage with high-speed data capabilities. Implementing such a system in mountainous regions, as illustrated by the Apuseni Mountains plane crash case study, can significantly enhance the effectiveness of emergency responses, ensuring that rescuers have the necessary tools to communicate and act swiftly in critical situations. “5G is a developing technology that would allocate substantial resources to enhancing QoS and system accomplishments” (Gutierrez, Caicedo, Campos-Delgado. 2021). Future research should validate these findings with real geospatial data and explore the broader applicability of this hybrid system in different terrains and scenarios.

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